

Antibody Characterization Report for Angiogenin

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Angiogenin

Gene name: *ANG*

Uniprot: P03950

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized three Angiogenin commercial antibodies for Western Blot and immunoprecipitation, using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. An HAP1 *ANG* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of Angiogenin protein in HAP1 is adequate as determined by DepMap [3].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC003507c001	CVCL_SC50	HAP1	ANG KO

Table 2: Summary of the Angiogenin antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab95389	GR212688-1	AB_10864903	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.850	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	14-9762-37*	1969044	AB_2865425	monoclonal	26-2F	mouse	0.500	other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-89249	VL3153022A	AB_2805443	polyclonal	-	rabbit	3.510	Wb

Wb=Western Blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested Angiogenin antibodies are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). Cells were starved in DMEM high-glucose containing L-glutamate and penicillin/ streptomycin.

Antibody screening by Western Blot on culture media

HAP1 WT and *ANG* KO (listed in Table 1) were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~18 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x g to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x g to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were concentrated by centrifuging at 4000 x g for 30 min using Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429).

Western Blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [4]. Western Blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual Western Blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106)

prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture media

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Starved HAP1 WT media were concentrated as described above and supplemented with protease inhibitor. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of protein were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and Western Blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels.

Figure 1: Angiogenin antibody screening by Western Blot on culture media

Figure 2: Angiogenin antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture media

Figure 1: Angiogenin antibody screening by Western Blot on culture media.

HAP1 WT and *ANG* KO were cultured in serum free media, and 35 µg of protein from concentrated culture media were processed for Western Blot with the indicated Angiogenin antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab95389 at 1/500; 14-9762-37* at 1/500; PA5-89249 at 1/500. Predicted band size: 16 kDa.
*=monoclonal antibody

Figure 2: Angiogenin antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture media.

Immunoprecipitation was performed on concentrate culture media from HAP1 WT, and using 2.0 µg of the indicated Angiogenin antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein G or protein A. Samples were washed and processed for Western Blot with the indicated Angiogenin antibody. For Western Blot, ab95389 was used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate.
*=monoclonal antibody

References

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